

www.arseam.com
Impact Factor: 0.98

EVALUATION OF ECONOMIC VALUE ADDED AS A PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT TOOL - A STUDY

¹Author: Ms. Pallavi Pahuja , ²Co author: Mr. Sandeep Passi
^{1&2} Assistant Professors,

Chandigarh Group of colleges , Landran, Mohali

ABSTRACT

In traditional method of computing the final results, compensation to labour and management is charged to profit and loss account. Cost of debt is also charged to the profit and loss account. Only the cost of equity capital is ignored. But in reality equity capital is scarce and has an opportunity cost, just as any factor of production. Yet traditional measures like ROI i.e. Return on investment, EPS i.e. Earning per share and Net Income does not account for the cost of equity capital.

Economic Value Added is computed by taking into account the cost of equity. Economic Value Added is basically the difference between the Net operating profit After Taxes and the cost of funds employed for that economic entity. It is a measure of economic efficiency of a company. Economic Value Added is also an indication of effectiveness in capital allocations. Economic Value Added is aimed to be a measure that tells us what has happened to the wealth of shareholders. It implies earning a return greater than the cost of capital, increases value and earning and earning less than the cost of capital decreases value.

But several empirical researches still contradict superiority of Economic value added as a performance measurement tool. In this research I have tried to compare Economic value added to some other traditional performance measures. As the objective of a good management is to increase shareholder's wealth so the performance measure which helps in predicting market value added more accurately would be considered a better performance measure . The significance of relationship of Economic Value Added and other traditional measures with Market value added is analyzed in this research which helps to evaluate effectiveness of the performance measurement tools.

In this study I have taken 30 large cap Indian companies as sample and analyzed the relationship of Economic Value Added and other traditional measures with Market value added of those companies.

Key words: Large Cap Companies, Economic Value, Market Value, Performance Measurement

Introduction

1.1 EVA: An Introduction

It is now well settled that the aim of every business entity should be to maximize shareholders wealth by enhancing the firm's value and all the activities of a firm should be directed to achieve this objective. Various theories of firm conceptualize a firm in various ways and provide an understanding of factors that contribute to the success of a firm. The *neo classical view* of the firm envisages a business entity as decision-maker based on the supply and demand of both input and output markets. *Organizational theory view* addresses aspects of a firm ignored by neoclassical economics. Disposing of the notion of the firm as a singular decision-maker and recognizing the firm as a complex organization encompassing multiple individuals, organization theory analyses the internal structure of the firm and the relationships between its constituent units and departments. The best explanation that has revolutionized the way we look at the business entity is given by Richard Coase who defined the business entity from a *Transaction cost view*. It explains the existence of the firm with respect to the reduction in costs of contractual arrangements between the buyers and sellers of productive resources. One can

say that the ability of the firm to continue to be competitive for generating surplus depends on its ability to reduce transaction costs between the buyers and sellers of the productive resources. The *network view* argues that the business entity once formed is not an isolated instance but a part of a social network, which can be defined as a set of nodes (e.g., persons, organizations) linked by a set of social relationships (e.g., friendship, transfer of funds, overlapping membership) of a specified type (Laumann, Galaskiewicz, and Marsden, 1978). In other words, an organization's productivity is determined less by its internal resources than by the set of resources that it can mobilize through its contacts. The more such contacts the firm has, the better it is 'plugged in' to the key task and influence processes of the industry, and the stronger is its strategic advantage (Madhavan, Balaji and John, 1998). The *Agency view and Stewardship view*, which are two opposite views regarding the conflict of interests between the various agencies involved in the management of the firm. Agency theory argues that unless managers are monitored constantly they act in self-interest, which might be at variance with interests of residual claimants most importantly those of shareholders. This variance can be reduced only through the added costs of monitoring or designing appropriate incentive structures (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). On the other hand the stewardship theory argues that managers interests lie in the well being of the organization and they are at variance with other stakeholders only when the managers' position is threatened due to environmental threats like mergers, acquisitions and takeovers (Donaldson, 1990). The *resource-based view* argues that the firm is bundle of tangible and intangible resources and an organization's success is dependent upon the efficient deployment of these resources to their best advantage (Grant 1991). The *knowledge based view* argues that the firm is a institution that creates an environment under which multiple individuals can integrate their specialist knowledge with low incentives designed to foster co-ordination between individual specialists, thus avoiding the problems of opportunism associated with high incentives directly related to knowledge transactions (Grant, 1996). The theories, taken together, explain that the success of the business entity in maximizing the firm-value depends on the effectiveness of integrating interests of the firms stakeholders and managers by designing suitable incentive scheme; by improving productivity of resources in the face of uncertainties, by efficient networking with other institutions and social agents; and by reducing transaction costs.

Performance Measurement: Investors measure overall performance of a firm as a whole to decide whether to invest in the firm or to continue with the firm or to exit from it. In order to achieve goal congruence, managers' compensation is often linked with the performance of the responsibility centers and also with firm-performance. Therefore selection of the right measure is critical to the success of a firm. To measure performance of a firm we need a simple method for correctly measuring value created/ enhanced by it in a given time frame. All the current metrics trade off between the precision in measuring the value and its cost of measurement. In other words, each method takes into consideration the degree of complexities in quantifying the underlying measure. The more complex is the process, the more is the level of subjectivity and cost in measuring the performance of the firm. There is a continuous endeavour to develop a single measure that captures the overall performance, yet it is easy to calculate. Each metric of performance claims its superiority over others. Performance of a firm is usually measured with reference to its past record and the performance of other firms with comparable risk profile. The various performance metrics currently in use are based on the returns on investment generated by the business entity . Therefore to reach a meaningful conclusion, returns generated by the firm in a particular year should be compared with returns generated by assets with similar risk profile (cross sectional analysis). Similarly return on investment for the current period should be compared with returns generated in past (time series analysis). A firm creates value only if it is able to generate return higher than its cost of capital. Cost of capital is the weighted average cost of equity and debt(WACC). The performance of a firm gets reflected on its valuation by the capital market. Market valuation reflects investor's perception about the current performance of the firm and also their expectation on its future performance. They build their expectations on the estimated growth of the business in terms of return on capital. This results in an incongruence between current performance and the value of the firm. Even if the current performance is better in relative terms, poor growth prospects adversely affects the value of the firm. Therefore any metric of performance, to be effective, should be able to not only capture the current performance but also should be able to incorporate the direction and magnitude of future growth. Therefore the robustness of a measure is borne out by the degree of correlation the particular metric has with respect to the market valuation.

Perfect correlation is impossible because as shown by empirical researchers, fundamentals of a company cannot fully explain its market capitalization, other factors such as speculative activities, market sentiments and macro-economic factors influence movement in share prices. However the superiority of a performance metric over others lies in providing better information to investors. Metrics of performance have a very important and critical role not only in evaluating the current performance of a firm but also in achieving high performance and growth in the future. The metrics of performance have a variety of users, which include all the stakeholders whose well being depends on the continued well being of the firm. Principal stakeholders are the equity holders, debt holders, management, and suppliers of material and services, employees and the end-users of the products and services. Value creation and maximization depends on the alignment of the various conflicting interests of these stakeholders towards a common goal. This means maximization of the firm value without jeopardizing the interests of any of the stakeholders. Any metric, which measures the firm value without being biased towards any of the stakeholders or particular class of participants, can be hailed as the true metric of performance. However it is difficult, if not impossible, to develop such a metric. Most of the conventional performance measures directly relate to the current net income of a business entity with equity, total assets, net sales or similar surrogates of inputs or outputs. Examples of such measures are return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA) and operating profit margin. Each of these indices measure a different aspect of performance, ROE measures the performance from the perspective of the equity holders, It is important to note that none of these measures truly reflect the complete picture by themselves but have to be seen in conjunction with other metrics. These measures are also plagued by the firm level inconsistencies in the accounting figures as well as the inconsistencies in the valuation methods used by accountants in measuring assets, liabilities and income of the firm. Accounting valuation methods are in variance with the methods that are being used to value individual projects and firms. The value of an asset or a firm, which is a collection of assets, is computed by discounting future stream of cash flows. The net present value (NPV) is the surplus that the investment is expected to generate over the cost of capital. Measures of periodical performance of a firm, which is the collection of assets in place, should follow the same underlying principles. Economic value added (EVA) is a measure that captures the valuation principles.

1.2 ECONOMIC VALUE ADDED – the concept

EVA is the most misunderstood term among the practitioners of corporate finance. The proponents of EVA are presenting it as the wonder drug of the millennium in overcoming all corporate ills at one stroke and ultimately help in increasing the wealth of the shareholder, which is synonymous with the maximization of the firm value. The attractiveness of the EVA lies in its use of cash flow and cost of capital that are determinant of the value of the firm. In the process, EVA is being bandied about with utmost impunity by all and sundry, which includes the popular press. The academic world in its turn has come up with various empirical studies which either supports the superiority of EVA or questions the claim of its proponents. Currently the empirical evidence is split almost half way.

EVA is nothing but a new version of the age-old residual income concept recognized by economists since the 1770's. Both EVA and 'residual income' concepts are based on the principle that a firm creates wealth for its owners only if it generates surplus over the cost of the total invested capital. So what is new? Perhaps EVA could bring back the lost focus on 'economic surplus' from the current emphasis on accounting profit. In a lighter vein it can be said that in an era where commercial sponsorship is the ticket to the popularity of even the concept of god, the concept of residual income has not found a good sponsor until Stern Stewart and Company has adopted it and relaunched it with a brand new name of EVA. Technically speaking EVA is nothing but the residual income after factoring the cost of capital into net operating profit after tax. But this is only the tip of the iceberg as will be seen in the next few sections. The paper examines EVA both as a measure of overall performance and a management philosophy that helps to improve the productivity of resources.

Mathematically:

$$EVA = (\text{adjusted NOPAT} - \text{cost of capital}) \times \text{capital employed}$$

Or

$$EVA = (\text{Rate of return} - \text{cost of capital}) \times \text{capital}$$

Where;

$$\text{Rate of Return} = \text{NOPAT} / \text{Capital}$$

Capital = total assets minus non interest bearing debt, at the beginning of the year

Cost of capital = cost of equity x proportion of equity + cost of debt (1-tax rate) x proportion of debt in the capital.

The above cost of capital is nothing but the weighted average cost of capital (WACC) Cost of equity is normally estimated using capital asset pricing model (CAPM) that estimates the expected return commensurate with the riskiness of the assets. If we define ROI as NOPAT/capital then the above equation can be rewritten as

$$EVA = (\text{ROI} - \text{WACC}) \times \text{CAPITAL EMPLOYED}$$

Capital being used in EVA calculation is not the book capital, capital is defined as an approximation of the economic book value of all cash invested in going-concern business activities, capital is essentially a company's net assets (total assets less non-interest bearing current liabilities), but with some adjustments:

Marketable securities and construction in progress are subtracted.

The present value of noncapitalized leases is added to net property, plant and equipment.

R&D expense is capitalized as a long-term asset and smoothly depreciated over 5 years (a period chosen to approximate the economic life typical of an investment in R&D).

Cumulative unusual losses (gains) after taxes are considered to be a long-term investment.

A firm can motivate its managers to direct their effort towards maximizing the value of the firm only by, first measuring the firm value correctly and secondly by providing incentives to managers to create value. Both are interdependent and they complement each other. Therefore this paper examines the EVA concept from two perspectives, EVA as a performance measure and EVA as a corporate philosophy. We shall examine EVA as a performance measure to assess whether it conveys any additional information to investors over conventional performance measures. In other words, whether information on EVA leads to better decision by investors. Examining EVA as a corporate philosophy we intend to look at the efficacy of EVA when implemented at every level of managerial decision making process to encourage managers to deploy resources only on value enhancing activities and to align the interests of shareholders with managers. This involves two things, one is linking managerial compensation package with EVA and second is to inculcate the culture of evaluating every action from the viewpoint that it should generate EVA. The ultimate outcome should be enhancement in the firm-value measured by the capital market. When EVA is used as a management philosophy, it results in the enhancement of productivity by continuously focusing on return vis-à-vis cost of capital. However as market discounts expected long term performance of the firm, any compensation that motivates enhancement of short term EVA, may not maximize the firm value. However with EVA culture, the firm as a whole focuses on the economic surplus and that definitely improves value enhancement process. Of course, this can be achieved even by implementing the other practices but the simplicity of EVA in communicating the very fundamental principle, that generation of surplus over cost of capital can only enhance the firm value, makes it a management technique superior to other planning and control techniques.

1.3 EVA AS A PERFORMANCE MEASURE

Proponents of EVA argue that EVA is a superior measure as compared to other performance measures on four counts:

- it is nearer to the real cash flows of the business entity;
- it is easy to calculate and understand;
- it has a higher correlation to the market value of the firm and
- its application to employee compensation leads to the alignment of managerial interests with those of the shareholders, thus minimizing the supposedly dysfunctional behavior of the management.

The last two merits can be considered as a reflection of the first two. If EVA truly represents the real cash flows of a business entity and it is easy to calculate and understand, then it automatically follows that it should be closely related to the market valuation and it should minimize the dysfunctional behavior of the management when used as an incentive measure. In other words, close relation to market valuation and convergence of managerial interests with shareholders interests is a vindication of EVA as a superior metric. EVA as a performance measure looks into the efficacy of EVA both as an absolute measure in comparison with net income, residual income and similar measures as well as a ratio in relation with performance measures like ROE, ROA and Operating Profit Margin, which are commonly used by both managers and equity analysts alike. These measures are normally used internally by the management to evaluate employee performance, incentive calculation and investment decisions and externally by equity analysts to ascertain the performance and growth of the firm. Along with these measures valuation models like NPV, IRR, Payback period and Book rate of return are used both internally and externally by managers for investment decisions. The former measures are backward looking measures which take into account past and current performance and facilitates prediction of future performance, whereas latter measures are more forward looking and discount the expected future cash flow streams associated with a given investment or new investment to ascertain the economic viability of the same.

1.4 The calculation of EVA and MVA and the link between EVA and MVA

A company's total market value is equal to the sum of the market value of its equity and the market value of its debt. In theory, this amount is what can be 'taken out' of the company at any given time. The market value added (MVA) is the difference between the total market value of the company and the economic capital (Reilly & Brown). The economic capital (invested capital) is the amount that is 'put into' the company and it basically refers to the fixed assets plus the net working capital.

$MVA = \text{Market value of company} - \text{invested capital}$

From an investor's point of view, MVA is the best external measure of a company's performance. Stewart states that MVA is a cumulative measure of corporate performance and that it represents the stock market's assessment from a particular time onwards of the net present value (NPV) of all a company's past and projected capital projects. The MVA is calculated at a given moment, but, in order to assess performance over time, the difference or change in MVA from one date to another can be determined to see whether value has been created or destroyed. Company creates value when $MVA > 0$, that is when the market value capital exceeds the capital invested. A negative value for MVA proves that the provisions concerning the ability of management to use efficiently the capital are unfavourable. MVA grows only if the additional capital invested generates a bigger return of present cost of capital. MVA doesn't take into account the dividend policy. A company which returns dividends has a bigger ability to create value than another with the same MVA, but without a dividend policy.

EVA is an internal measure of performance that determines MVA. A company's EVA is the fuel that fires up its MVA.' As defined by Stern Stewart Management Services of New York City, EVA is the difference between a company's net operating income after taxes and its cost of capital of both equity and debt. EVA measures the surplus value created by a firm in its existing environment. It's a strategy formulation and a financial performance management tool that helps companies make a return greater than the firm's cost of capital. Firm adopt this concept to track their financial position to guide management decisions regarding resource allocation, capital budgeting and acquisition analysis.

The economic principle is that the firm must earn more on its funds than the cost of those funds or it is not creating value. Unlike traditional profitability measures, both MVA and EVA measures take into account the cost of equity capital. MVA is most appropriate for investor owned healthcare organizations and EVA is the best measure for not-for-profit organizations.

MVA assesses the effect of managerial actions on shareholder wealth from an organization's inception, while EVA assesses managerial effectiveness in a given year.

EVA is calculated as follows:

$$EVA = (Rate\ of\ return - cost\ of\ capital) \times capital$$

Where;

$$Rate\ of\ Return = NOPAT/Capital$$

Capital = total assets minus non interest bearing debt, at the beginning of the year

Cost of capital = cost of equity x proportion of equity + cost of debt (1-tax rate) x proportion of debt in the capital.

The ROIC minus the WACC is also called the 'return spread'. If the return spread is positive, it means the company is generating surplus returns above its cost of capital and this translates into a higher MVA. Lehn and Makhija describe EVA as follows: "EVA and related measures attempt to improve on traditional accounting measures of performance by measuring the economic profits an enterprise – after-tax operating profits less the cost of the capital employed to produce those profits". The link between EVA and MVA is that MVA is the present value of all the future EVAs a company is expected to generate, discounted at the WACC.

2.1 Literature Review

Bhattacharya and Phani have analyzed Economic Value Added from different angles. Economic Value Added as a performance measure has definitely an edge over the traditional methods. By considering the cost of capital it has helped in increasing the wealth of shareholders. As a corporate philosophy it can certainly be used for improving the productivity. When used as an incentive compensation measure, it tends to improve the value of the firm by inducing managers towards value creating activities. The study relied on empirical studies in U.S.A. and other advance economies. It concluded that though EVA does not provide additional information to investors, it can be adapted as a corporate philosophy for motivating and educating employees to differentiate between value creating and value destructing activities. This would lead to direct all efforts in creating shareholder value. The paper brings to attention the dangerous trend of reporting EVA casually that might mislead investors. The authors have also referred to the growing usage of Economic Value Added as a measure of internal and external reporting. However its calculation involves significant subjectivity and this reduces its informative value. Moreover it fails to provide better signals to the capital market as compared to conventional accounting measures like ROI, however hard selling of EVA has contributed positively in highlighting the fundamental economic principle, long forgotten by managers. In India companies are using EVA internally as a performance measure for improving productivity that would lead to enhancement of shareholder value.

However a dangerous trend has also set in, to use EVA casually for external reporting. This trend should be stalled as such reporting might mislead users of those reports.

Madhu Malik , has analyzed various dimensions of Economic Value Added. She has made a extensive attempt to decipher Economic Value Added and analyze its superiority over traditional profit based performance measures with special reference to a detailed study of Hindustan lever limited. In the study she tried to compare different financial performance measures and analyze their significance in explanation for variation in shareholder's wealth. In this context various financial performance measures like Return on net worth (RONW), Return on asset (ROA), Earnings before interest and taxes (EBIT), Earning per share (EPS) and some other financial variables were compared with Economic Value Added. Comparing Economic Value Added with traditional measure the author found that not even a single traditional performance metric explains to the fullest extent variation in shareholder's wealth. The author has concluded that the use of traditional measures have presented very rosy picture but, the use of Economic Value Added gives more relevant information.

Karam Pal Singh and Mahesh C. Garg have analyzed Economic Value Added of some Indian companies and ranked and statistically examined any variation in ranking if any occurs. They have analyzed Economic Value Added for companies as well as for industries. Thus provide a broader perspective of Economic Value Added and its significance in performance evaluation. The authors found that only a few industries are reporting negative Economic Value Added and rest are generating positive Economic Value Added, and that suggest a good picture. But actually about two third of the companies of the companies have been able to have positive Economic Value Added only. This happens when you analyzed an industry excellent financial performance of some of the companies sometimes create difference . For the study period the relationship between Economic Value Added and Net Operating Profit After Taxes was been observed significantly high for almost all the years. The study has thrown some light on the problems that can occur or misleading information that can be harmful in performance measurement.

Balachandran , had examined the investing decisions of the firms by classifying Economic value added adopters based on the performance measure they had previously employed. The author has hypothesised that firms that previously used ROI – based measures are facing an under investment problem and that switching to an Economic value added – based measure will result in an increase in investment and a decrease in cash distributed to shareholders. He has found that the results are significantly consistent with his predictions for firms switching from earning based measures, but insignificant results for the other partition of firms. So, the study is holding good for the assessments that are made for the firms which switches from earning based measure to Economic value added based measure.

Aggarwal has explained the Economic Profit (EP), Economic value added, Shareholder value added and other measures used in maximizing shareholder's wealth. A comparison has been made between economic and accounting profits. The author has also discussed the nature of reported profits and agency costs. The author has laid down the issues in using Economic profit to reduce agency costs and the challenges in developing an Economic profit based system..

Damodaran (1998) has described Economic value added as a measure of dollar/ rupee surplus value, not the percentage difference in returns. It is closest to the net present value of a project in capital budgeting, as opposed to the internal rate of return. The value of a firm, in discounted cash flow terms can be written in the terms of Economic value added. Both Economic value added and the discounted cash flow valuation should provide the same estimate for the value of a firm. The author has concluded that the information that is required for both approaches is exactly the same expected cash flow over time. A policy of maximizing the present value of Economic value added over time should be equivalent to the policy of maximizing firm's value.

Anupam, has evaluated many financial performance measurement tools which are been used by the Indian companies. The results found by the researcher are on contrary side of the other findings. The study suggests that among all measures Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) is the main determinant of the Market Value Added in India. In the study Return on Capital Employed emerged as the most superior tool for measuring the

performance of a company. The relationship of Economic Value Added with the dependent variable is not very significant and so does not support effectiveness of Economic Value Added as a performance measurement tool.

3.1 Research Objectives

Following are the objectives for which the study is been conducted :

1. To evaluate Economic Value Added as a performance measure tool for Large-cap Indian companies.
2. To see relationship between Economic Value Added and other financial variables in Indian companies.
3. To see whether Economic Value Added is a superior performance measurement tool for or not than the earning based traditional measurement tools like ROCE and RONW.

4.1 Research Methodology

The research will be performed by observation of Indian companies listed under Bombay Stock Exchange . The annual reports of the companies will be taken under observation to compute their Market value added, Economic value added, Return on Net worth and Return on Capital Employed for a time period of five year. The time period for the observations will be last six financial years i.e.2003-04, 2004-05, 2005-06, 2006-07, 2007-08 and 2008-09.

4.1 Sample Design

The sample consists of thirty large cap companies listed on Bombay Stock Exchange. A judgemental sampling method is used for selection of companies. There is an effort made to select companies from diverse industries for an appropriate outcome. Since the research aims at evaluation of Economic value added as a helping tool for investors the sample should cover significant market , so I have selected the companies which cover more than 60 % of total market capital of the companies registered at Bombay stock exchange. Also the sample consists of companies, which cover a wide area so that the research would help in evaluation of EVA for several industries.

4.2 Data Gathering

Relevant data are be collected from the compilation of CMIE prowess database for last six financial years. Official websites of companies, Annual reports of the companies, Websites providing financial data of companies (like moneycontrol.com) were also been searched for data collection and confirmation of correctness of the data. Economic Value Added was computed from the available data by subtracting cost of capital employed from Net Operating Profit after Tax in rupee terms. Similarly Market value added is calculated as the difference the total market value of the company and the economic capital Return on net worth, Return on Capital Employed were computed as according to our assumptions from the information provided in balance sheets and income statements .

4.3 Data Processing and Analysis

Correlation analysis is used to examine the relationship between Market value added, Economic Value Added and other financial variables which are Return of Net Worth and Return on Capital Employed. Also coefficient of determination (R^2) is used to assess whether Economic Value Added is more correlated to Market value added than traditional performance measures or not.

5.1 Analysis

Correlation Matrix For Ambuja Cements

		Market value added/ Economic capital(EC)	Economic Value Added / Economic Capital(EC)	Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Return on Equity (ROE)
Market value added/ EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	1.00	0.200 0.704	0.262 0.616	0.036 0.946
Economic Value Added/EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.200 0.704	1.00	0.925 0.005	0.977 0.001
Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.262 0.616	0.925 0.005	1.00	0.983 000
Return on Equity (ROE)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.036 0.946	0.977 0.001	0.983 000	1.00

* Correlation is Significant at the 0.05 level (2- tailed)

The correlation matrix of Ambuja Cements is given in the above table which suggests that RONW and ROCE are positively correlated with market value added and the correlation analysis for them is statistically significant.

Correlation Matrix For Bajaj Auto

		Market value added/ Economic capital(EC)	Economic Value Added / Economic Capital(EC)	Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Return on Equity (ROE)
Market value added/ EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	1.00	0.381 0.456	0.938 0.006	0.923 0.009
Economic Value Added/EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.381 0.456	1.00	0.224 0.670	0.230 0.662
Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.938 0.006	0.224 0.670	1.00	0.997 000
Return on Equity (ROE)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.923 0.009	0.230 0.662	0.997 000	1.00

* Correlation is Significant at the 0.05 level (2- tailed)

The correlation matrix of Bajaj Auto again shows the same i.e., RONW and ROCE are positively related to market value added and the correlation analysis is significant for them. Economic value added is also positively correlated with market value added but the relationship is not significant.

Correlation Matrix For BHEL

		Market value added/ Economic capital(EC)	Economic Value Added / Economic Capital(EC)	Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Return on Equity (ROE)
Market value added/ EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	1.00	0.510 0.301	0.858 0.029	0.959 0.002
Economic Value Added/EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.510 0.301	1.00	0.266 0.610	0.230 0.559
Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.858 0.029	0.266 0.610	1.00	0.891 0.020
Return on Equity (ROE)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.959 0.002	0.230 0.559	0.891 0.020	1.00

* Correlation is Significant at the 0.05 level (2- tailed)

The correlation matrix of BHEL shows all the financial measures are positively correlated with market value added significantly but the relationship of RONW and ROCE is stronger than with EVA.

Correlation Matrix For Bharti Tele

		Market value added/ Economic capital(EC)	Economic Value Added / Economic Capital(EC)	Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Return on Equity (ROE)
Market value added/ EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	1.00	0.591 0.217	-0.322 0.534	-0.324 0.531
Economic Value Added/EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.591 0.217	1.00	0.501 0.311	0.527 0.282
Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	-0.322 0.534	0.501 0.311	1.00	0.946 0.004
Return on Equity (ROE)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	-0.324 0.531	0.527 0.282	0.946 0.004	1.00

* Correlation is Significant at the 0.05 level (2- tailed)

Bharti tele’s correlation matrix shows that only EVA is positively correlated with market value added . But the relationship of MVA with RONW and ROCE is not significant statistically.

Correlation Matrix For CIPLA

		Market value added/ Economic capital(EC)	Economic Value Added / Economic Capital(EC)	Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Return on Equity (ROE)
Market value added/ EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	1.00	0.958 0.003	0.007 0.989	0.309 0.471
Economic Value Added/EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.958 0.003	1.00	0.171 0.747	0.531 0.278
Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.007 0.989	0.171 0.747	1.00	0.679 0.138
Return on Equity (ROE)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.309 0.471	0.531 0.278	0.679 0.138	1.00

* Correlation is Significant at the 0.05 level (2- tailed)

For CIPLA the correlation matrix shows all the measures are positively correlated with MVA, but the relationship between EVA and MVA only is significant statistically.

Correlation Matrix For Grasim

		Market value added/ Economic capital(EC)	Economic Value Added / Economic Capital(EC)	Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Return on Equity (ROE)
Market value added/ EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	1.00	0.150 0.776	0.112 0.833	0.103 0.846
Economic Value Added/EC	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.150 0.776	1.00	0.898 0.015	0.915 0.010
Return on Net Worth (RONW)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.112 0.833	0.898 0.015	1.00	0.998 0.000
Return on Equity (ROE)	Pearson coeff. Significance t – value (2-tailed)	0.103 0.846	0.915 0.010	0.998 0.000	1.00

* Correlation is Significant at the 0.05 level (2- tailed)

In correlation matrix of Grasim given in table above, all the measures are positively correlated with market value added but none of them are correlated with MVA significantly.

6. Interpretation of year wise analysis

The results clearly brings out that the ROCE is the most significant variable in all the years. RONW is the next best variable with the correlation being significant positive in all the years under the study.

The relationship of Economic value added with the dependent variable has not turned to be significant for any year. So as per the correlation analysis Economic value added can not be called an effective performance measurement tool.

Thus as per the correlation analysis of all the six years that are taken for the study shows that

Economic value added is not the supreme measure. Return on capital employed is most effective measure among the performance measure analyzed under the study as it is having highest positive significant relation with the dependent variable Market value added.

7. References

- A. Amin and D. M. Hossain, "Economic Value Addition: From Stakeholders Point of View," *The Bangladesh Accountant*, 2004, pp.106-108.
- I. Issham, "Performance of Public-Listed Companies in Malaysia: Using EVA," 2010.
- J. Forker and R. Powell, "Does EVA Beat Earnings? Evidence on Associations with Stock Returns and Firm Values—Revisited," *EAA Meeting*, Prague, 1-3 April 2004, pp. 301-336.
- J. J. Cordeiro, and D. D. Kent Jr., "Do EVA Adopters Outperform Their Industry Peers? Evidence from Security Analyst Earnings Forecasts," *American Business Review*, Vol. 19, No. 2, 2001, pp. 57-6
- M. Haque, M. Akter and N. C. Shil, "Value-Based Measure: An Application of Eva in Small Manufacturing Company in Bangladesh," *Munich Personal RePEc Archive*, No. 7711, 2004, p. 12. <http://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/7711/>
- M. Houle, "Economic Value Added," *Liberty University*, Lynchburg, 2008.
- N. Venkatraman and R. Vasudevan, "Measurement of Business Performance in Strategy Research: A Comparison of Approaches," *Academy of Management Review*, Vol. 11, No. 4, 1986, pp. 801-814.
- P. Erasmus, "Value Based Financial Performance Measures: An Evaluation of Relative and Incremental Information Content," *Corporate Ownership & Control*, Vol. 6, No. 1, 2008, pp. 66-77.
- W. Fredrik, "Value Based Management: Economic Value Added or Cash Value Added?" *Corporate Ownership & Control*, Vol. 6, No. 1, 1997, pp. 66-77.